

High voltage, high frequency, high bandwidth sweeping arbitrary waveform challenge

Overall design concept

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Abstract—Particle accelerators utilize high voltage, high magnetic fields, and radio frequencies range amplifiers in order to guide and accelerate the particle beam. Particle beam modulation is a new challenge in accelerator design and research in high energy physics. Article deal with challenges into particle accelerators beam modulators from a power electronics point of view.

Keywords—Radio-frequency amplifiers, Amplitude modulation, High-voltage techniques, Signal synthesis, Particle accelerator,

I. INTRODUCTION

Starting from 1930, when Cockcroft and Walton built the first DC particle accelerator, different types of particle accelerators were built and today achieve the speed very close to the light speed and energies up to 6.5 TeV per beam.

At the same time, some research topics and applications, like "Facility for Anti-Proton and Ion Research" (FAIR), need an intensity-modulated electron beam [1], [2].

Initial electron gun lens (modulator) requirements were:

Peak current	10A
Extraction voltage	22,3kV
Modulation bandwidth	5MHz
Frequency	<1MHz
Waveform frequency sweep & period	-
Amplitude compression ratio during the frequency sweep	-
Calculated grid-cathode capacitance	-

After design updates and computer simulations, the primary modulator technical values are:

Extraction voltage	22,3kV
Arbitrary waveform	Gaussian, double Gaussian, flat-top
Modulation voltage, peak-to-peak	0...-3200V
Waveform frequency sweep	400 kHz... 1000 kHz
Waveform frequency sweep period	~150 ms
Modulation bandwidth	6,5 MHz
Amplitude compression ratio during the frequency sweep	0,4MAX ... 1MAX
Calculated grid-cathode capacitance	75pF
Grid-cathode capacitance, real	100 pF...125pF

Electron beam gun and modulator operating principle is similar to Cathode Ray Tube (CRT) operating principle: the heated cathode emits electrons and applied anode voltage accelerate and move electron to target, thus creating an electron beam [3]. In order to change the beam intensity, the negatively charged grid step in and keep some amount of emitted electrons into space between cathode and grid, under high vacuum condition, of course. By changing the negative grid voltage against cathode, the beam intensity changes.

Below are described the problems in solving this high voltage, radio-frequency, arbitrary waveform challenge. Here aren't described the well-known basics of the fundamental theory of RF amplifier design.

II. KNOWN PROBLEMS AND QUESTIONS

Particle accelerators utilize more and more electronic devices. The main problem - the behavior of the particle accelerator is filled with X-rays, γ -rays, high level of other electromagnetic emissions; thus, semiconductor devices cannot be applied. The structure of semiconductors is destroyed under such radiation conditions.

Today are known some radiation-resistant semiconductor devices but not for high voltage application. Such devices are used in aerospace, nuclear reactor, and weapons communities for many years but different tasks.

High DC and waveform peak-to-peak values are the next obstacles in semiconductor utilization - there are no high voltage and radio-frequency bandwidth semiconductors on the market [4]. The closest one - DE475-102N21A RF Power MOSFET max source-drain voltage $VDSS < 1000V$ and 30MHz Maximum Frequency [5]. Others, like MRF150 or BLF188, are 50V $VDSS$ [6],[7].

Thus, the only solution seems to apply vacuum tube devices. Fortunately, some radio-frequency high voltage vacuum tube models - triodes, tetrodes, and pentodes still are produced. Vacuum tube application - mainly forgotten technique in power electronics - require different technical design solutions like semiconductor application.

Radio-frequency high bandwidth amplifiers are based on three keywords: frequency, resonance, and impedance.

The grid-cathode capacitance is the main problem: the impedance of this capacitance (125 pF) change from 3183 Ohm to 182 Ohm over the waveform bandwidth 6,5 MHz. Practically, it is not known that one has designed a 0...-3kV and 6,5 MHz bandwidth linear amplifier for 400 kHz to 1000kHz arbitrary waveform first harmonic frequency sweep if the load impedance over the bandwidth changes 17 times.

High voltage isolation for signal transmission to isolate low voltage waveform generator and accelerator electron gun high voltage side require radio-frequency 6,5 MHz bandwidth, up to several hundred watts rated power, up to 60 kV galvanic isolation transformer.

III. ARBITRARY WAVEFORM GENERATION AND SPECTRUM

The necessary Gaussian waveform are shown on Fig.1 and the corresponding amplitude compression and bandwidth on Fig.2.

Fig.1. Necessary Gaussian, double Gaussian and flat-top waveforms

Fig.2. Amplitude compression (top) and bandwidth (bottom)

The block diagram of the arbitrary waveform generator are shown on Fig.3.

The generator includes a linear ramp (sawtooth) generator to drive VCO (Voltage Controlled Oscillator). VCO clock FPGA. Waveform data are stored at datafile. FPGA output data

values to high-speed DAC with the frequency set by VCO and through signal compressor necessary waveform is generated.

Fig.3. Waveform generator block diagram.

VCO frequency sweeps in the range 40 MHz to 100 MHz. The full period is 150 ms.

The practically generated waveform are shown on Fig.4.

Fig.4. Generated waveform, oscilloscope image

IV. POWER AMPLIFICATION CHALLENGE

A. Vacuum tube electrical characteristics

Design relay on high voltage RF vacuum tubes, for the reasons mentioned above.

High voltage RF power valves like 3-500GZ are under consideration. The main volt-ampere curves at grounded grid connection are shown on Fig.5. A grounded grid amplifier is preferred due to several known reasons, not described here.

Fig.5. 3-500GZ curves, grounded grid connection.

It is convenient to define the linear tube amplifier operation by applied grid-cathode voltage: A, B, AB1, AB2 class.

Some basic connection schematic (A class amplifier) are shown on Fig.6 [8]. In this case, amplifier efficiency is not essential.

Fig.6. A class amplifier amplification principle [7].

A brief explanation of vacuum tube class AB1 and AB2 working conditions and class are shown on Fig.7.

Fig.7. AB1 and AB2 class amplifier amplification principle [7]

AB1 or AB2 classes are better efficiencies with acceptable signal distortion.

B. Wideband low-pass filter

Known RLC Low-pass allow compensating grid-cathode capacitance change over the desired bandwidth if filter $Q=0,707$ or $d=1$. Gun cathode-grid capacitance here is a filter output capacitor.

There are several drawbacks when RLC filter is applied as a vacuum valve amplifier load:

- For 3200 V peak-to-peak output voltage the input voltage must be the same value.
- Amplifier output impedance is much higher than RLC filter input impedance $R1, R2$, so RLC circuit does not act as designed $R2L1C1$ filter (Fig.8.)

Fig.8. RLC filter and amplifier output connection

C. Waveform amplitude modulation

In general, to solve the changing load impedance problem, a well-known carrier amplitude modulation (AM) technique can be implemented. High radio-frequency carrier is modulated (multiplied) by required arbitrary signal waveform. The resulting signal spectrum, including carrier frequency and two side-bands, are shown on Fig.9, according to the simplified expression(1):

$$u(t) = A_c \sin \omega_c t \times A_s \sin \omega_s t \quad (1)$$

where:

A_c and ω_c - carrier amplitude and frequency respectively,
 A_s and ω_s - signal amplitude and frequency, respectively.

Fig.9. Amplitude modulation bandwidth shift and two sidebands shown

Amplitude modulated signal includes frequency f_c carrier signal and two sidebands Δf - upper and lower - as well as the original waveform signal in the low-frequency range. Following band-pass filter cut all other frequencies, not in lower or upper sidebands. Higher filter Q allows us to achieve better filtration; thus, the result of the expression (2) must be in range 10-20:

$$\frac{f_c}{2\Delta f} = 10 \dots 20 \quad (2)$$

It is evident that in this case, f_c must be in the range of 130 MHz...260 MHz.

The popular amplifier circuit diagram are shown on Fig.10. [9], [10].

Fig.10. LC tank and load impedance matching circuit

The necessity of the high voltage high-frequency signal rectification after amplification technically is very challenging - to combine frequency, impedances, and high voltage.

D. Waveform SSB modulation

Known Single Sideband Modulation (SSB) result is just upper or lower sideband; thus, the modulation frequency must be in the range 65 MHz...130 MHz.

The general question here is SSB signal demodulation: carrier frequency f_c must be subtracted from signal spectrum $f_c \dots f_c + 6,5$ MHz (upper sideband, for example) before rectifier. A very challenging task for the high voltage system.

Another problem is the measurements. The possibility to see real grid-cathode voltage waveform and measure real peak-to-peak voltage could be a not only advantage - that is necessary for further experiments and calculations.

As a conclusion - none AM or SSB modulation are handy to develop such a system.

E. Measurements

High voltage high-frequency measurements, as well as signal form observation, is a challenge by itself. Measurement circuits and elements must be included in the overall electric design. Such measurement circuits can be evaluated as parasitic capacitances or inductances from some point of view and tuning elements will allow to exclude them. At the same time - typically tuning is done by a human, not available here due to high voltage. Possible, electromagnetic, remotely operated tuning devices will be included.

The planned electron gun cathode-anode voltage is 22,3 kV, as mentioned above. All measurement devices isolation design must stand significantly higher voltage for safe work.

V. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

The experimental setup is shown in Fig.11. On the top is located an RF amplifier, the electron gun is located on the stand on the right. Additional power sources like gun cathode heater power source as well as an anode power source are located on the shelves under the RF power amplifier. There isn't something special in the overall setup.

The experiments were provided on an electron mini-gun: 1000 V anode-cathode voltage and grid cathode voltage up to 100 V, close to Gaussian waveform as shown on Fig.4, including frequency 100 step sweep.

The results of the experiments show waveform high sensitivity to load impedance change during the frequency sweep.

Regardless that experiments with small electron gun show acceptable results, scaling up to 3200 V peak-to-peak seems not possible.

A different technique, devices, and solutions must be applied instead of the RF linear amplifier.

VI. FUTURE WORK

Design of radio-frequency 4kV isolated and radiation-resistant voltage divider is a very complicated task, not solved yet.

Another modulator technical idea and solutions are under development on the current stage. Results will be reported as soon the results will be obtained.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGMENT

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Fig.11. Experimental setup

REFERENCES

1. Ondreka D., Spiller P., Apse-Apsitis P., Schulte K., OVERCOMING THE SPACE CHARGE LIMIT: DEVELOPMENT OF AN ELECTRON LENS FOR SIS18, Proceedings of IPAC2017, Copenhagen, Denmark, available: <http://accelconf.web.cern.ch/AccelConf/ipac2017/papers/tupva059.pdf>
2. ARIES, <https://aries.web.cern.ch>
3. Martin A., "Cathode Ray Tubes for Industrial and Military Applications", in Hawkes, Peter (ed.), Advances in Electronics and Electron Physics, Volume 67, Academic Press, 1986, p. 183, ISBN 9780080577333,
4. Frey R., Capabilities of Low-cost High Voltage RF Power MOSFETs at HF and VHF, Microsemi APTB 981, available: https://www.microsemi.com/document-portal/doc_download/14713-high-voltage-high-efficiency-mosfet-rf-amplifiers-design-procedure-examples.
5. DE475-102N21A RF Power MOSFET, available: https://eu.mouser.com/datasheet/2/240/DE475_102N21A_00_Datasheet_RevA-1591739.pdf
6. MRF150 datasheet, available: <https://eu.mouser.com/datasheet/2/249/MRF150-318373.pdf>
7. BLF188XR datasheet, available: <https://www.ampleon.com/products/broadcast/0-500-mhzrf-power-transistors/BLF188XR.html>
8. RCA transmitting tubes, Technical manual, Radio Corporation of America, 1962
9. available: https://www.w8ji.com/Vacuum_tube_amps.htm
10. Whitaker, Jerry C. "Chapter 4 – Designing Vacuum Tube Circuits", Power Vacuum Tubes Handbook 2nd Edition, Boca Raton: CRC Press LLC, 2000

